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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE REACTIVITY OF THE AUTONOMIC NERVOUS SYSTEM AND THE BIRTH PROCESS IN WOMEN IN LABOR WITH THE NORMOCHROMIC TYPE OF BLOOD CIRCULATION.....10
2. **Karabayeva A. Marjona, Khudoyarova R. Dildora**
CHANGES IN THE MOTHER-PLACENTA-FETUS SYSTEM IN WOMEN IN LABOR WITH IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA WITH A MODERATE PREDOMINANCE OF THE TONE OF THE SYMPATHETIC NERVOUS SYSTEM.....17
3. **Tillabayeva M. Dilnoza**
DYSMENORRHEA IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS ON THE BACKGROUND OF POSTCOVOID SYNDROME.....23

HEALTHCARE

4. **Madazimov M. Madamin, Mamasoliev S. Nematjon, Botirov A. Jakhongir**
PREVENTIVE AND PREVENTIVE ISSUES OF CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE POPULATION OF DIFFERENT AGES, TOPICAL ISSUES AND MAIN PRIORITIES (LITERATURE REVIEW)31

THERAPY

5. **Tashkenbaeva N. Eleonora, Rakhmanov Kh. Bakhodir, Kholikov B. Ikhtiyor**
FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH SYSTOLIC DYSFUNCTION OF THE RIGHT VENTRICLE IN PATIENTS WITH A HISTORY OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION41
6. **Akhmedova Sh.Nilufar, Makhmudov B.Ravshan**
RISK OF DEVELOPING CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE WITH OBESITY AND A MODERN APPROACH TO DIAGNOSIS.....51
7. **Karamatullaeva E. Zebo, Ibragimova F. Elnara**
THE ROLE OF BLOOD COAGULATION INDICATORS IN CORONAVIRUS INFECTION DISEASE.....57
8. **Khasanjanova O. Farida, Yorbulov S. Laziz**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF THE CARDIOPROTECTOR TRIMETAZIDINE ON THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION COMPLICATED BY CHRONIC HEART FAILURE IN YOUNG PATIENTS63
9. **Amirova A. Shokhidabonu**
STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF SELECTIVE BETA-BLOCKERS ON 24-HOUR BLOOD PRESSURE MONITORING.....70

SURGERY

10. **Rakhmanov E. Kosim, Davlatov S. Salim, Radjabov P. Jasur**
ANALYSIS OF RELAPSE OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND THE ROLE OF MORPHOLOGICAL MODIFICATION.....76
11. **Aslanov G. Valijon, Xujabaev T. Safarboy**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS IN ACUTE ADHESIVE SMALL INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION.....83
12. **Kurbaniyozov B. Zafar, Mukhiddinov X. Bobur, Askarov A. Pulat**
IMPROVEMENT OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHOLECYSTOCHOLEDOCHOLITHIASIS.....89

13. **Utayev H. Latifjon, Dusiyarov M. Muhammad, Askarov A. Pulat**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF STARGED VENTRAL HERNIA COMPLICATED WITH
INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION.....95
14. **Sayinaev K. Farrukh, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Rakhmanov E. Kasim**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF
PATIENTS WITH POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS103
15. **Ilkhomov E. Oybek**
CURRENT VIEWS ON MINOR INVASIVE CORONARY SURGERY.....111
16. **Rizaev A. E'zozbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
THE IMPORTANCE OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ACUTE
PANCREATITIS SURGERY.....120
17. **Rizaev A. E'zozbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
PROGNOSIS OF THE SEVERITY OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS ACCORDING TO THE
RESULTS OF LAPAROSCOPY AND THE BALTHAZAR SCALE129

PEDIATRICS

18. **Devorova B. Marifat**
ETIOPATHOGENESIS, METHODS OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF FOOD
ALLERGIES IN CHILDREN.....139
19. **Ibatova M. Shoira, Abdullaeva E. Mavjuda, Mamatkulova Kh. Dilrabo**
SOME ASPECTS OF PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN145
20. **Ibatova M. Shoira, Mamatkulova Kh. Feruza**
SOME ASPECTS OF GIARDIASIS IN CHILDREN.....151

CHILDREN SURGERY

21. **Abdullaev B. Zafar, Agzamkhodjaev T. Saidanvar**
CONTEMPORARY COMPLEX TREATMENT OF BLADDER EXSTROPHY IN
CHILDREN.....157
22. **Ollabergenov T. Odilbek, Terebaev A. Bilim, Nematov Sh. Alisher**
TRANSANAL ENDORECTAL SURGERY BY DE LA TORRE MONDRAGON AS A
METHOD OF CHOICE IN YOUNG CHILDREN WITH HIRSCHSPRUNG'S DISEASE.169

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

23. **Indiaminova N. Gavkhar**
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEETH FISSURAL SEALING IN THE
PREVENTION OF CARIES OF PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN WITH DAUN
SYNDROME.....176

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

24. **Omonova Sh. Maftuna, Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna**
EFFICIENCY OF MICROWAVE IMMUNOMODULATION DURING SPECIFIC
HYPOSENSIBILIZATION IN PATIENTS WITH POLLINOSIS.....184
25. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Makhkamova E. Nigora, Usmanova A. Nilufar,
Normuradov A. Nodirjon**
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOSCOPIC ADENOTOMY AND
MYRINGOTOMY IN PATIENTS WITH EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA AND AUDITORY
TUBE DYSFUNCTION189

26. **Makhkamova E. Nigora, Nabiyeva M. Djamila**
DIAGNOSIS OF PATHOLOGY OF THE NASAL CAVITY AND PARANASAAL SINUSES
IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL CLEFT LIP AND PALATE.....197

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

27. **Khakimova Z. Sokhiba, Kodirov A. Umid, Mukhammadiyeva Dilafruz**
THE RESULTS OF EXAMINATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT IN
PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH PAIN SYNDROME WITH COMPRESSION-ISCHEMIC
DORSOPATHY.....209
28. **Khakimova Z. Sokhiba, Kodirov A. Umid, Fayzullayev Ganisher**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR DORSOPATHY OF RHEUMATIC ORIGIN.....216
29. **Mirdjurayev M. Elbek, Adambayev I. Zufar, Samiyev S. Asliddin, Ergashev B. G'ulom**
MODERN PROBLEMS OF DORSALGIA IN MODIC TYPE SPONDYLODISCITIS.....223
30. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL ASPECTS OF ANXIETY-PANIC DISORDERS IN EPILEPSY.....230
31. **Mamatqurbonov B. Shokirjon**
FEATURES OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS IN EPILEPSY IN
RESIDENTS OF MOUNTAIN AND DESERT AREAS.....235
32. **Mamatqurbonov B. Shokirjon**
FEATURES OF NEUROVISUALIZATION DISORDERS IN IDIOPATHIC AND
SYMPTOMATIC EPILEPSY IN RESIDENTS OF MOUNTAIN AND DESERT AREAS,
CONSIDERING THE CSF CRANIAL INDEX.....245

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

33. **Yusupbekov A. Abror., Tillyashaykhova M. Rano, Tuychiyev P. Anvar**
DEVELOPMENT OF THERAPEUTIC AND DIAGNOSTIC TACTICS FOR NON-
MUSCLE-INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER USING MINIMALLY INVASIVE
TECHNOLOGIES.....255
34. **Rakhimov M. Nodir, Shakhanova Sh. Shakhnoza**
SARCOPENIA THROUGH THE EYES OF AN ONCOLOGIST AND RADIATION
DIAGNOSTIC METHODS.....266
35. **Akramov R. Akhtam**
DRUG THERAPY OF MALIGNANT TUMORS (CHEMOTHERAPY, TARGETED
THERAPY, IMMUNOTHERAPY).....275

MORPHOLOGY

36. **Khamidova M. Farida, Nurullayev A. Javohir**
ON THE ISSUE OF MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF KERATODERMA IN
DIABETES MELLITUS284
37. **Khamidova M. Farida, Ruzikulov Zh. Sobir**
GENETIC ASPECTS OF NEWBORN RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME.....292
38. **Abdirashidova A. Gulnoza, Gafurov A. Farrukh**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY MECHANISMS OF OBESITY IN TYPE I DIABETES.....299
39. **Usanov S. Sanjar, Abduraimov A. Zafarjan**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LIVER TISSUE OF
GROUP FIFTH WHITE RATS305

40. **Toshmamatov N. Bakhtiyor, Djumanova E. Nargiza**
CHANGES IN THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF
THE GASTRIC WALL IN POLYPRAGMASS WITH ANTI-INFLAMMATORY
DRUGS.....312
41. **Ergashev S. Suhrob S., Niyozov T. Shuhrat, Djurabekova T. Aziza**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF PERINATAL HYPOXIA IN ANIMAL
EXPERIMENTS.....318

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

42. **Rizaev J. Alimdjanovich, Khusainboev Sh., Davronbekovich**
SYMPTOMS, CAUSES AND TREATMENTS FOR SHOULDER INJURIES
(LITERATURE REVIEW)324
43. **Rizaev J. Alimdjanovich, Khusainboev Sh., Davronbekovich**
MODERN ASPECTS OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF OVERWORK SYNDROME IN
ROWERS.....331
44. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov A. Azim, Raxmonov N. Temur**
CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL CLUBFOOT IN INFANTS
(LITERATURE REVIEW).....337
45. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov A. Azim**
THE ROLE OF BREASTFEEDING NEWBORNS.....346
46. **Mamatkulov Kh. Oybek, Khusainboev D. Shokhrukhbek**
KNEE JOINT INJURIES DURING SPORTS.....354
47. **Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh, Onorboyev A. Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF ARTHROSCOPIC PARTIAL MENISCECTOMY.....362
48. **Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh, Onorboyev A. Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF PLASTY OF THE ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT USING THE
HAMSTRING TENDONS.....368
49. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Eranov F. Nurali, Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh**
ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE CARPAL BONES IN
CHILDREN AND CHARACTERISTICS OF INJURIES.....374

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

50. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Shoimov U. Shukrillo**
EPIDEMIOLOGY AND MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF MODERN ROAD
TRANSPORT INJURIES AND VEHICLE INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....382
51. **Olimova M. Madinabonu**
COMPARISON OF ROAD TRANSPORT ACCIDENTS IN UZBEKISTAN AND
RUSSIA.....389
52. **Beknazarov Y. Shokir, Khasanova A. Mukarrama., Beknazarov Sh. Jahongir**
PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS OF SCIENTISTS OF MEDICAL
UNIVERSITIES OF NEW UZBEKISTAN IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL EVIDENCE OF
FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION QUALITY398

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

53. **Ergasheva Ya. Munisa, Yarmukhamedova A. Nargiza, Mallakhodjayev A. Anvarkhon**
ROLE OF ENTEROVIRAL INFECTION IN THE FORMATION OF SEROUS
MENINGITIS.....404
54. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Ergasheva Ya. Munisa**
IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES410

55. **Djuraeva S. Kamola, Niyazova A. Tajigul**
CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF BRUCELLOSIS
IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE.....418
56. **Achilova M. Matlyuba. Bayjanov K. Allabergan, Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza**
INFLUENCE OF ANTI-PROTOZAL THERAPY ON THE NUMBER OF CD4+
LYMPHOCYTES IN HIV INFECTION WITH HYAMBLYOSIS AND
BLASTOCYSTOSIS.....428
57. **Karamatullaeva E. Zebo**
FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF SEROUS MENINGITIS OF MUMPS ETIOLOGY IN
ADULTS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAMARKAND REGION).....435
58. **Rustamova A. Shahlo, Vafokulova Kh. Nargiza**
THE EFFECT OF CESAREAN SECTION ON THE INTESTINAL MICROFLORA IN
NEWBORNS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....443

DERMATOVENEROLOGY

59. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Imamov S. Otabek, Abduvakhitova N. Indira**
ROLE OF ENDOGENOUS INTOXICATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HERPES-
ASSOCIATED EXUDATIVE ERYTHEMA MULTIFORME.....451
60. **Khamidova M. Farida, Khusinova A. Firuza**
GENETIC FACTORS OF ACNE.....457

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THE RESULTS OF EXAMINATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT IN PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH PAIN SYNDROME WITH COMPRESSION-ISCHEMIC DORSOPATHY

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ABSTRACT

In 2021-2023, in the city hospital of Samarkand, we examined 55 patients with pain syndrome with dorsopathy of compressive ischemic origin, of which 31 (56.4%) were women and 24 were men (43.6%), studied standardized clinical and cluster analysis was used to process instrumental indicators. It was shown that spinal cord degenerative diseases are a cascading process that develops over time. Diagnostic studies are aimed at identifying these changes. It is especially important to determine the compression of the root to choose treatment tactics.

Key words: compression dorsopathy with ischemic genesis, ischiuradiculoalgia, chronic dorsopathy, osteochondrosis.

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С БОЛЕВЫМ СИНДРОМОМ С КОМПРЕССОРНО-ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ ДОРСОПАТИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В 2021-2023 годах в городской больнице Самарканда нами обследовано 55 пациентов с болевым синдромом с дорсопатией компрессионно-ишемического генеза, из них 31 (56,4%)

женщины и 24 мужчины (43,6%), изучен стандартизированный клинический и кластерный анализ. была использована для обработки инструментальных показателей. Показано, что дегенеративные заболевания спинного мозга представляют собой каскадный процесс, развивающийся во времени. Диагностические исследования направлены на выявление этих изменений. Особенно важно определить компрессию корня для выбора тактики лечения.

Ключевые слова: компрессионная дорсопатия ишемического генеза, ишиорадикулоалгия, хроническая дорсопатия, остеохондроз.

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SIQILISH-ISHEMIK GENEZLI DORSOPATIYASI BO'LGAN OG'RIQ SINDROMI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARNI TEKSHIRISH NATIJALARI VA DAVOLASHNING SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

2021-2023-yillarda Samarqand shahar shifoxonasida biz siqilish ishemik genezli dorsopatiya bilan og'riq sindromi bo'lgan 55 bemorni tekshirdik, ulardan 31 (56,4 %) ayollar va 24 erkaklar (43,6%) bemorda o'rganilgan standartlashtirilgan klinik va instrumental ko'rsatkichlarini qayta ishlash uchun klaster tahlili qo'llanildi. Orqa miya degenerativ kasalliklari vaqt o'tishi bilan rivojlanadigan kaskadli jarayon ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Diagnostik tadqiqotlar ushbu o'zgarishlarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Davolash taktikasini tanlash uchun ildizning siqilishini aniqlash ayniqsa muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: siqilish ishemik genezli dorsopatiya, isxioradikuloalgiya, surunkali dorsopatiya, osteoxondroz.

Kirish. Siqilish-ishemik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyalari mushaklarning muntazam ravishda uzoq davom etadigan statik kuchlanishiga, bir xil turdagi harakatlarga, oyoq-qo'llarning majburiy holatiga, chuqur egilishlarga, shuningdek uzoq vaqt tik turish yoki o'tirishga ega bo'lgan harakatlar natijasida rivojlanadigan o'zgarmas pozitsiya hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqot usullari: Biz siqilish ishemik genezli dorsopatiya bilan og'riq sindromi bo'lgan 55 bemorni tekshirdik, ulardan 31 (56,4 %) ayollar va 24 erkaklar (43,6%).

1-rasm. Bemorlarning jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi.

1-rasm: bemorlarning jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi ko'rsatilgan. Ayollarning o'rtacha yoshi 40 yosh bo'lib, maksimal yoshi 70, eng kam esa 18 yoshni tashkil qilgan. Erkaklarning o'rtacha yoshi 41, maksimal yoshi 60, eng kam esa 20 yosh edi. Barcha bemorlarning asosiy shikoyatlari

surunkali og'riqlar bo'lib, lokalizatsiya bo'yicha 14 (25,5%) bemorda bo'yin, ko'krak qafasi - 3 (5,45%), bel - 35 (63,6%), bo'yin va ko'krak - 2 (3,63%) umurtqa pog'onasi va 1 (1,81%) bemorda isxioradikuloalgiya kuzatildi.

2-rasm. Bemorlarning og'riqlarni tarqalish lokalizatsiyasi

Ba'zi hollarda bemorlar boshga - 10 (18,2%), qo'llar - 14 (25,5%) va oyoqlarga - 31 (56,3%) tarqaladigan og'riqni boshdan kechirdilar. Kasallikning boshida asosan bel mintaqada tarqalgan og'riq, nosimmetrik ikki tomonlama xarakterga ega bo'lib, ma'lum bir sohada yanada mahalliyashtirilgan. Bemorlarning 54,9% doimiy (to'mtoq) og'riq bezovta qildi. To'satdan harakatlarni amalga oshirishda 12 (21,8%) holatlarda og'riq chidab bo'lmas holga bo'ladi, 4 (7,3%) kuyuvchi tabiatli og'riq, 9 (16,3%) "o'q tekandek", 6 (11%) "elektr toki urishi" kabi sodir bo'ladi. Ba'zi bemorlarda og'riqlar og'irlilikni ko'tarish - 28 (51%), oldinga egilish - 16 (29,1%), yo'tal - 14 (25,6%) bilan qo'zg'atilgan. Bemorlar tez-tez uyg'onish - 28 (51%) va uyqusizlik - 45 (81,8%), asab tizimining keyingi asteniyasi bilan shikoyat qildilar, chunki uyqusizlikdagi noqulay harakatlar og'riqni keltirib chiqardi.

Ikkita (3,6%) bemorda o'choq L1-L3 darajasida kuzatilgan, shikoyatlari sonning ichki va old yuzasi bo'ylab o'tkir og'riqlargacha kamaygan. Bel umurtqalarning L4-L5 darajasida shikastlanishi bilan 34 (61,8%) bemorlar sonning lateral yuzasi va oyoqning oldingi yuzasi bo'ylab to'piqqacha bo'lgan kuyishuvchi og'rig'idan shikoyat qildilar.

Anamnezdan kasallik asta-sekin, noto'g'ri bajarilgan harakatlar, mushaklarning statik kuchlanishi, shuningdek, o'zgarmagan holatda uzoq vaqt turish yoki o'tirish natijasida boshlangan.

3-rasm: Bemorlarda asosiy shikoyatlarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi:

Tadqiqot natijalari: Subyektiv ko'rsatkichlarni tahlil qilish natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, bemorlarda og'riq o'tkir, ba'zi hollarda o'tkir osti kechishi qayd etilgan. 18% hollarda qo'zg'atuvchi omillarsiz to'satdan spontan og'riq paydo bo'lishi kuzatilgan.

Kasallikning o'rtacha davomiyligi o'rtacha 4 yil 4 oyni tashkil etdi, bu kasallikning surunkaliligini ko'rsatdi. Kasallikning kuchayishi yiliga bir marta - 6 bemorda (10,9%), yiliga 2 marta - 32 (58,1%), yiliga 3 marta - 17 (30,9%). Kuchlanishning davomiyligi 10 dan 16 kungacha. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, o'rganish davrida kuchlanish chastotasi vaqt o'tishi bilan asta-sekin o'sib bordi va kuchlanish davomiyligi 16 dan 25 kungacha uzoqroq bo'ldi. Shuni ham ta'kidlash kerakki, kuchlanish oralig'idagi remissiyalar to'liq bo'lmagan.

4-rasm. Rivojlanishni qo'zg'atuvchi asosiy omillar siqilish-ishemik kelib chiqadigan surunkali dorsopatiya

Qo'zg'atuvchi omillar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, ko'pincha (37,8%) og'riq og'ir yuklarni ko'tarishdan keyin boshlangan, 18,3% hollarda og'ir yuk ko'tarish va gipotermiya omillarining kombinatsiyasi bilan kuchaygan va 14,6% hollarda faqat gipotermiya sodir bo'lgan. Bemorlarning 2,4 foizi uyqu buzilishini qayd etdi. Gipotermiya va stress kabi qo'zg'atuvchi omillarning kombinatsiyasi 12,2%, og'irlikni ko'tarish va stress - 4,9%, uyqu buzilishi va gipotermiya - 1,2%, shuningdek,adekvat bo'lmagan yuklama 8,5% ni tashkil etdi.

Obektiv holati: bemorlarning umumiy ahvoli qoniqarli, ongi ravshan, holati passiv, nafas olish tezligi daqiqada 16 dan 28 martagacha o'zgarib turadi va o'rtacha 22, puls daqiqada urish tezligi 65 dan 86 gacha, o'rtacha 76 ga teng, o'rtacha arterial bosim 130/85 mm Hg ust, limfa tugunlarining kattalashishi aniqlanmagan.

Nevrologik holat. Ong aniq, barcha bemorlarda joy, vaqt, vaziyat va o'z-o'zidan orientatsiya saqlanib qoladi. 41 (75%) bemorda faol harakatlar oralig'ida cheklov aniqlandi. Obektiv umurtqa pog'onasi nevrologik tekshiruvini ushbu guruhdagi barcha bemorlarda 55 (100%) umurtqali deformatsiyalarni aniqladi.

1-jadval.

Bemorlarni asosiy nevrologik belgilarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi

Simptom	Jami N=55	
	abs	%
nevropatik og'riq	29	52,7
VASH bo'yicha og'riq darajasi	35	63,6
oyoq yoki qo'llarga tarqaladigan yonish xususiyatli og'riq	23	41,8

bel lordozning tekislanishi	38	69
chanoq soxasidagi og'riq	30	54,5
tik turgan holatda yuzaki mushaklarning kuchlanishi	27	49
yotgan holatda yuzaki mushaklarning kuchlanishi	34	61,8
qo'l yoki oyoqdagi zaiflik	34	61,8
reflekslarning pasayishi	20	36,4
tendon reflekslarining prolapsi	10	18,2
zararlangan ildizning innervatsiya zonasida gipoesteziyasi	31	56,4
zararlangan ildizning innervatsiya zonasida giperesteziya	11	20
Lassega sinamasining ijobiy belgisi	28	51
uyqusizlik	18	32,7
allodiniya	10	18,2
Orqa miya rentgenogrammasi - osteoxondroz belgilari (bo'g'im bo'shlig'ining torayishi; osteofitlarning shakllanishi; sariq ligament va umurtqalararo ligamentlarda degenerativ-distروفik o'zgarishlar.	55	100
MRT va MSKT protruzionlar va churra intervertebral disklar belgilari	15	27

Barcha bemorlar (N=55) neyrovizual tadqiqotlaridan o'tkazildi.

Xulosa: Orqa miya degenerativ kasalliklari vaqt o'tishi bilan rivojlanadigan kaskadli jarayon ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Klinik ko'rinishlar murakkab o'zgarishlar, jumladan, osteoxondroz, spondiloz, osteoartrit tufayli yuzaga keladi, ular ko'pincha tug'ma moyillik bilan kuchayadi. Diagnostik tadqiqotlar ushbu o'zgarishlarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Davolash taktikasini tanlash uchun ildizning siqilishini aniqlash ayniqsa muhimdir. Yuqoridagi harakatlar distروفik ta'sirlangan disk sohasidagi disfiksatsiya bilan bog'liq bo'lgan siqilish ishemik genezli dorsopatiyaning dastlabki namoyon bo'lishiga olib keladi, uning tolali halqasining yaxlitligi saqlanib qolishi yoki buzilishi mumkin. Ta'sirlangan disk hududida mikrosirkulyatsiya qon aylanishi buzilgan taqdirda, ishemiyani qo'zg'atadigan va sinuvertebral asab retseptorlarini siqib chiqaradigan diskemiya kuzatiladi.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. – vol. 7. – No. 6. (in Russ)
2. Khakimova S.Z., Atokhodjaeva D.A., Hamrokulova F.M. Research Of Motor Function In Patients With Chronic Pain Syndrome At Radiculopathies Of Different Genesis. The American Journal of Applied sciences, 2020. 2 (10), 14-21.
3. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.O. Comparative correlation of markers of inflammatory metamorphism in peripheral blood in dorsopathies of various origins //Uzbek journal of case reports. – 2022. 2(2). 12-18. (in Russ).
4. Samiyev A.S, Xakimova S.X, Soibnazarov O.E. Rehabilitation of patients under spine surger. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022;7(1):139-44.
5. Utkurovna S.G., Farkhodovna, K.F., Orifjonovna O.F, Features of immune mechanisms in the development of pathological processes,2022 ,2 (82), 108-115.
6. Axmedova D.A., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Features of post-stroke depression in the early and late recovery periods" Innovative Science, 2015, 6(2), 224-227 (in Russ).
7. Burieva D.M., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Comparative study of the function of maintaining a vertical posture in healthy foxes and patients with parkinsonism" Innovative science, 2015. 6(2) 232-236 (in Russ).
8. Dadasheva M.N., Razilova A.V., Boldin A.V. Possibilities of practical use of dexketoprofen in pain syndrome of various etiologies. 2018. 16(10),32–36. (in Uzb).

9. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022. 7(6). (in Russ).
10. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.A. Features of clinical and neurological results of examination of patients with dorsopathies of rheumatic origin // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. 7(1). (in Russ).
11. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B. K., Kodirov U.A. Study of motor function in patients with chronic pain syndrome with dorsopathies of various origins // tools, mechanisms and technologies of modern innovative development. – 2022. 243-251. (in Russ).
12. Khakimova S.Z. Chronic brucellosis in the real practice of a neurologist: (clinical diagnosis and treatment). Benefits of clinical and experimental medicine, 2019;1 (3), 133–138. (in Russ).
13. Rizaev Zh. A., Khaidarov N. K. Clinical , epidemiological and etiopathogenetic study of ischemic stroke // Journal of Neurology and Neurosurgical Research. – 2020. – Т. 1. – No. 1.
14. Abdullayev Afzal, Kubayev Aziz, Rizayev Jasur . Excitability threshold in neuritis of the lower alveolar nerve. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022, vol. 7, issue 4, pp.238-245
15. Rizaev , Zh., Raimova , M., Boboev , K., & Abdullaeva, M. (2019). Parkinson's: classification, clinical picture and basics of treatment. Stomatologiya , 1(1(74), 64–67

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БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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